

RUBEANIC ACID AND ITS DERIVATIVES AS COLORIMETRIC REAGENTS. PART III. *NN'*-DI- β -HYDROXYETHYL- AND *NN'*-DI-*iso*AMYL-RUBEANIC ACIDS

By J. XAVIER AND PRIYADARANJAN RAY

The effect of substitution in rubeanic acid on its reactivity as a reagent has further been investigated by examining the behaviour of (I) *NN'*-di- β -hydroxyethyl- and (II) *NN'*-di-*iso*amyl-rubeanic acids. Substitution of a hydrogen atom by a hydroxyl in the ethyl radical of diethylrubeanic acid increases the solubility of the product and of its metallic complexes (e.g. of copper) in certain solvents. Di-*iso*amyl-rubeanic acid behaves like other disubstituted alkyl derivatives. Both the reagents, if used in caustic alkali solution, retard the colour development, as in the case of the diethyl derivative (cf. Part II, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 589). This retardation effect is more pronounced with the increase in the chain length of the substituent. Methods for the spectrophotometric determination of copper (using I), cobalt (using II), nickel (using II), palladium (using I & II) and ruthenium (using I) have been described.

In continuation of our previous work (Parts I & II, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 432, 589) *NN'*-di- β -hydroxyethyl- and *NN'*-di-*iso*amylrubeanic acids have been studied as colorimetric reagents. The substitution of a hydroxyl group in the ethyl radical has been found to increase the solubility of the product and of its metallic complexes in certain organic solvents. The spectrophotometric determination of copper also has therefore been possible, using *NN'*-di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid. *NN'*-Di-*iso*amylrubeanic acid behaved like other disubstituted alkyl derivatives of the acid (*loc. cit.*). Methods for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt and nickel with this reagent have been developed in alcoholic pyridine medium as in the case of the parent compound. The use of a caustic alkali solution of the reagent was, however, found to retard the colour development. Similar retardation was observed, though to a much less extent, with *NN'*-diethyl and *NN'*-di- β -hydroxyethyl derivatives. It may be noted that as the chain length of the substituent increases, this retardation effect becomes increasingly pronounced. Curiously, however, if the alkali be added after the addition of the reagent, the formation of the coloured complex occurs as usual in all these cases. An explanation of this behaviour may, probably, be found in the structural change of the reagent in alkali solution which might hinder the assumption of a favourable configuration for the complex formation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Reagents.—The preparation and properties of *NN'*-di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid, (HO.H₂C.CH₂.NH.CS.CS.NH.CH₂.OH), have not been reported in the literature. It was prepared, like other alkyl-substituted rubeanic acids, by warming (40-50°) rubeanic acid with an alcoholic solution of ethanolamine (in molar proportions). The product was cooled in ice, when orange-red crystals separated out along with some sulphur. These were filtered and the hydroxy compound was purified by repeated crystallisation from ethyl alcohol; yield about 50-60% of the theoretical. (Found: N, 13.48; S, 31.13. Calc. N, 13.45; S, 30.78%).

The product forms rhombic plates from alcohol, m.p. 93-94°. It is sparingly soluble in cold water, but more easily in ethyl alcohol and other common organic solvents.

NN'-Di-isoamylrubeanic acid, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}\cdot(\text{CH}_3)_2$, was prepared by warming rubeanic acid with an alcoholic solution of isoamylamine (Wallach and Reinhardt, *Annalen*, 1891, 262, 354). The substance crystallises out in yellowish plates (lit. red prisms) from alcohol, m.p. 59-60°.

Reaction with Metal Ions.—The complex compounds formed by *NN'*-di- β hydroxyethyl- and *NN'*-di-isoamyl-rubeanic acids with metallic salts resemble those formed by rubeanic acid and its other derivatives. The properties of these complexes are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Metal.	<i>NN'</i> -Di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid.	<i>NN'</i> -Di-isoamylrubeanic acid.
Cu ^{II} .	Green ppt., acquires a violet tinge on keeping (from ammoniacal, neutral or weakly acetic acid soln.); very sparingly soluble in benzene or toluene, but fairly soluble in pyridine (greenish yellow soln. extractable by isoamyl or isobutyl alcohol).	Green ppt. with blue tinge (from ammoniacal, neutral or weakly acetic acid soln.); very sparingly soluble in common organic solvents, but more easily in pyridine (greenish yellow colour).
Co ^{II} .	Brownish yellow ppt. (from ammoniacal solution); very sparingly soluble in toluene or isoamyl alcohol, but fairly soluble in pyridine (orange-yellow colour, partially extractable by isoamyl or isobutyl alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate).	Dark brown ppt. (from ammoniacal soln.); fairly soluble in benzene, toluene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, isoamyl or isobutyl alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate and pyridine (orange-yellow colour, extractable by the above solvents).
Ni ^{II} .	Deep violet ppt. (from ammoniacal soln.); fairly soluble in pyridine (orange-red colour, extractable by isoamyl or isobutyl alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate).	Same as I; pyridine soln. (rose-red colour, extractable by isoamyl or isobutyl alcohol and ethyl or amyl acetate).
Pd ^{II} .	Orange-red ppt. which appears on keeping the soln. (acid soln.); fairly soluble in alcohol, acetone, isoamyl or isobutyl alcohol and easily in pyridine (deep yellow colour, extractable by isoamyl or isobutyl alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate and chloroform).	Deep red ppt. (from acid soln.); soluble in almost all the common solvents. The pyridine soln. (yellow or orange-yellow, extractable by isoamyl or isobutyl alcohol).
Ag ^I .	Pale yellow ppt. (from neutral soln.); soluble in excess of alcohol, giving an orange-yellow soln.	Yellow ppt. from neutral soln., slightly soluble in alcohol.
Pb ^{II} .	Yellow ppt. from alkaline soln., soluble in excess of alkali.	Same as I.
Fe ^{III} .	Orange-yellow soln. from which a brown ppt. separates on standing (from acid soln.).	Yellow ppt. from acid soln.
Au ^{III} .	Same as above.	Golden yellow colour.
Hg ^{II} .	White ppt. from neutral soln., stable towards dilute alkali.	Same as I.
Ru ^{III} .	Blue colour in alcoholic acid soln.	Blue soln. from which a precipitate appears in a short time.

Spot Tests.—Copper, cobalt, nickel and palladium can be detected by the spot plate technique, under conditions similar to those stated in the case of other substituted rubeanic acids (*loc. cit.*). Copper gives a greenish black precipitate on the surface of the drops, cobalt and palladium, a yellowish brown coloration, and nickel, a pink coloration, in about five minutes after the drops are placed in the depression of the spot plate. The identification and concentration limits are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Metal.	Identification and concentration limits.	
	<i>NN'</i> -Di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid.	<i>NN'</i> -Di-isoamylrubeanic acid.
Copper	0.0507 ($1:8 \times 10^6$)	0.057 ($1:8 \times 10^6$)
Cobalt	0.025 ($1:1.6 \times 10^6$)	0.03 ($1:1.3 \times 10^6$)
Nickel	0.025 ($1:1.6 \times 10^6$)	0.02 ($1:2 \times 10^6$)
Palladium	0.060 ($1:5 \times 10^6$)	0.10 ($1:3 \times 10^6$)

Spectrophotometric Determinations

NN'-Di- β hydroxyethylrubeanic acid serves as a useful reagent for the determination of copper, palladium and ruthenium, but not for that of cobalt and nickel. The cobalt complex is fairly soluble in pyridine, but the resulting solution is rather unstable, especially at high concentrations of cobalt. The colour intensity of an alcoholic pyridine solution of nickel-di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid was found to attain its maximum value only after a long time (about 18 to 24 hours), from preparing the solutions. The determination of nickel, using the reagent, was therefore quite unsatisfactory. Cobalt, nickel and palladium can all be determined by using *NN'*-di-isoamylrubeanic acid. As with *NN'*-dimethyl- and *NN'*-diethyl-rubeanic acids (*loc. cit.*), the pyridine solution of copper-di-isoamylrubeanic acid was found to be unstable.

Copper was, however, determined by *NN'*-di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid in acetone-pyridine medium. Cobalt and nickel were estimated in alcoholic pyridine solution using *NN'*-di-isoamylrubeanic acid. Palladium was determined by both the reagents in alcoholic solution. Ruthenium was determined using *NN'*-di- β hydroxyethylrubeanic acid in a manner similar to that followed for rubeanic acid (Part I, *loc. cit.*).

An alcoholic solution of the reagents (0.1%) was used in all the experiments. Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer, glass cells of 5, 10 and 20 mm cross section and a Cambridge Bench Type p_H -meter, with glass or alkali electrodes and a saturated calomel electrode as the reference electrode, were used.

Determination of Copper

The green copper complex of *NN'*-di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid dissolves in pyridine, yielding a greenish yellow solution. This affords a ready means of determining

copper spectrophotometrically. An acetone-pyridine medium was found to be the most suitable for the purpose. An alcoholic or aqueous pyridine medium, on the other hand, gives uncertain results with gradual precipitation of the complex.

FIG. 1
Absorption curves.
Cell length = 10 mm.

- Curve I. Copper—di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid; 2 p.p.m. Cu; p_H 10.7.
 Curve II. Cobalt—di-isoamylrubeanic acid; 1 p.p.m. Co; p_H 10.5.
 Curve III. Nickel—di-isoamylrubeanic acid; 2 p.p.m. Ni; p_H above 10.2.
 Curve IV. Palladium—di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid; 2 p.p.m. Pd; p_H 3.5.
 Curve V. Palladium—di-isoamylrubeanic acid; 1.75 p.p.m. Pd; p_H 3.5.
 Curve VI. Ruthenium—di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid; 2 p.p.m. Ru.

Absorption maximum.—No maximum in the visible region of the spectra was observed (cf. curve I, Fig. 1). Measurements were made at 390 $m\mu$, where the reagent blank gave comparatively a low absorption.

Pyridine concentration: 10 c.c. in 25 c.c. final volume made up with acetone. With 5 c.c. of pyridine and 1 c.c. of the reagent solution (0.1%), the test solution, containing 2 p.p.m. Cu, remained clear only for about 20 to 30 minutes, whereas when 10 c.c. of pyridine was added, the optical density of the solution remained unaltered for about 20 hours.

Reagent concentration: 1 c.c. of 0.1% alcoholic solution of the reagent was sufficient to develop the maximum intensity for copper up to 4 p.p.m.

Optimum p_H range: 10.1—11.0.

Beer's law was obeyed (cf. curve I, Fig. 2).

Stability of the colour.—The maximum intensity was reached within 5 to 10 minutes after the addition of the reagent and making up the volume with adjustment of p_H . The intensity thereafter remained unchanged for several hours at room temperature.

Sensitivity: 0.007 γ Cu/cm² (Sandell) and 0.03 γ Cu/cm² (practical).

Effect of diverse ions.—Many metals were found to interfere. The use of complexing agents like the disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetra-acetic acid to mask the interference due to cobalt, nickel, iron, chromium, etc., was not possible, as the copper colour due to *NN'*-di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid was also partially masked.

Procedure.—To the copper solution, free from interfering ions, pyridine (10 c.c.), the reagent solution (0.1%, 1 c.c.) and acetone (10 c.c.) were added. The volume was made up to 25 c.c. with acetone, after adjusting the p_H to 10.1 to 11.0. The optical density was measured at 390m μ against the reagent blank.

Determination of Cobalt

The orange-yellow colour of the cobalt salt of *NN'*-di-*iso*amylrubeanic acid was developed in alcoholic pyridine solution.

Absorption maximum: 380–400 m μ (cf. curve II, Fig. 1). Measurements were made at 400 m μ .

Pyridine concentration: 5 c.c. of pyridine in a total volume of 25 c.c. made up with alcohol.

Reagent concentration: 1 c.c. of 0.1% alcoholic solution.

Optimum p_H range: Above 10.2. The intensity remained unchanged above this p_H , unless the solution was made excessively alkaline.

Beer's law was obeyed up to 2 p.p.m. Co. The solutions became turbid with higher concentrations of the metal.

Stability of the colour.—A solution containing 1 p.p.m. Co (p_H 10.5) showed constant optical density for 3–5 hours. The stability of the solution decreased appreciably (precipitation occurs within 5–10 minutes) when the cobalt concentration was greater than 2 p.p.m.

Sensitivity: 0.0056 γ Co/cm² (S) and 0.03 γ Co/cm² (p).

Effect of diverse ions: As under rubeanic acid (*loc. cit.*).

Procedure.—To the test solution 5 c.c. of pyridine and 1 c.c. of the reagent solution were added. The p_H was adjusted to about 10.5 and the volume made up to 25 c.c. with alcohol (95%). The optical density was measured at 400 m μ against the reagent blank.

Determination of Nickel

Nickel develops a rose-red colour in alcoholic pyridine solution by the addition of *NN'*-di-isoamylrubeanic acid.

Absorption maximum: 510 $m\mu$ (cf. curve III, Fig. 1). The reagent solution has practically little absorption at this wave-length.

Pyridine concentration: 5 c.c. of pyridine in a total volume of 25 c.c. made up with alcohol.

Reagent concentration: 1 c.c. of the reagent solution (0.1%) in alcohol was sufficient for 4 p.p.m. Ni, above which 2 c.c. of the reagent was required for the maximum development of colour.

Optimum p_H range: Above 10.2; slight variations in the alkalinity of the solution above this p_H value (up to 11.5) did not affect the colour intensity.

Beer's law was obeyed (cf. curve III, Fig. 2).

FIG. 2
Beer's law curves.
Cell length = 10 mm.

- Curve I. Copper - di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid; 390 $m\mu$; p_H 10.5 - 11.0.
 Curve II. Cobalt - di-isoamylrubeanic acid; 400 $m\mu$; p_H 10.2.
 Curve III. Nickel - di-isoamylrubeanic acid; 510 $m\mu$; p_H above 10.2.
 Curve IV. Palladium - di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid; 390 $m\mu$; p_H 3 - 4.
 Curve V. Palladium - di-isoamylrubeanic acid; 395 $m\mu$; p_H 3 - 5.
 Curve VI. Ruthenium - di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid; 625 $m\mu$.

Stability of the colour.—The optical density of a solution containing 6 p.p.m. Ni remained unchanged for more than 24 hours at the room temperature.

Sensitivity: 0.00737 Ni/ cm^2 (S) and 0.037 Ni/ cm^2 (p).

Effect of diverse ions: As under rubeanic acid.

Procedure.—Same as that followed for cobalt using the same reagent. After making up the volume, the optical density was measured at 510 $m\mu$ against the reagent blank.

Determination of Palladium

(a). *Using NN'-Di-β-hydroxyethylrubeanic Acid.*—When an alcoholic solution of NN'-di-β-hydroxyethylrubeanic acid is added to a palladium solution, an orange-yellow colour is developed.

Absorption maximum: 390 mμ (cf. curve IV, Fig. 1).

Concentration of alcohol: It was observed that a minimum concentration of about 75% ethyl alcohol in the medium was necessary to prevent the precipitation of the complex.

Reagent concentration: 1 c.c. of 0.1% alcoholic solution of the reagent was needed to develop the maximum colour intensity for palladium up to 8 p.p.m.

Optimum p_H range.—The colour development was almost instantaneous in slightly acid medium ($p_H \sim 1.0$); a further increase in p_H (up to 9.0) was found to have no effect on the colour intensity.

Beer's law: Obeyed up to 6 p.p.m. Pd (cf. curve IV, Fig. 2).

Stability of the colour: The optical density remained unaltered for about 24 hours.

Sensitivity: 0.0117 Pd/cm² (S) and 0.057 Pd/cm² (p).

Effect of diverse ions.—At p_H 3–4, presence of cobalt (100γ) and nickel (10γ) can be tolerated for 2γ Pd/c.c. Lead, cadmium, zinc, manganese, etc. do not cause any interference. Addition of phosphoric acid eliminated the interference due to traces of iron (50γ for 2γ Pd/c.c.), in which case the solutions were made up with 1:1 aqueous alcohol. Copper, vanadate, molybdate and tungstate, when present even in very small amounts, interfere.

Procedure.—The reagent solution (1 c.c.) was added to the palladium solution and the volume made up to 25 c.c. with ethyl alcohol after adjusting the p_H between 3 and 4. The optical density was measured at 390 mμ against the reagent blank.

(b). *Using NN' di-isoamylrubeanic Acid.*—The same procedure was followed as with NN'-di-β-hydroxyethylrubeanic acid.

Colour: Orange-yellow.

Absorption maximum: 385–395 mμ (cf. curve V, Fig. 1). Measurements were made at 395 mμ.

Alcohol and reagent concentration: Same as in the previous case.

Optimum p_H range: 2.5–9.0. Measurements were made at p_H 3–5.

Beer's law was obeyed up to 6 p.p.m. Pd (cf. curve V, Fig. 2).

Stability of the colour: Same as in (a).

Sensitivity: 0.0106γ Pd/cm² (S) and 0.047 Pd/cm² (p).

Effect of diverse ions: Same as in (a).

Procedure: Same as under (a). The optical density was measured at 395 mμ.

Determination of Ruthenium

NN'-Di- β -hydroxyethylrubeanic acid reacts exactly in the same manner with ruthenium^{III} salt solutions as rubeanic acid itself. The same procedure (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*) was therefore followed for the colour development. The absorption maximum was, however, found to lie between 600 and 650 $m\mu$ (cf. curve VI, Fig. 1). The minimum amount of the mixture (1:1) of concentrated hydrochloric acid (11 *N*) and ethyl alcohol (95%) required for the maximum colour development was 4 c.c., and the corresponding reagent concentration for Ru up to 5 p.p.m. was 1 c.c. (0.2% acetic acid solution). The optical density was measured at 625 $m\mu$. The system obeyed Beer's law (cf. curve VI, Fig. 2) up to 8 p.p.m. Sensitivity was 0.0117 Ru/cm² (S) and 0.047 Ru/cm² (p), *i.e.* same as for rubeanic acid.

DEPARTMENT OF INORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE,
JADAVPUR, CALCUTTA-32.

Received May 24, 1958.